

APPLICATIONS FOR COMPOSITES IN THE OFFSHORE ENVIRONMENT

P. C. OLIVER *F.P.R.I.*

Bathos Developments Ltd., Stonehaven, Scotland

Non corroding materials are of the utmost importance for low maintenance high reliability in any marine application. For the majority of structural purposes, however, cost considerations dictate the specification of steel and concrete; both active and passive protective measures are employed in order to ensure an acceptable level of safety and cost.

Increasing awareness of the properties of composite materials is opening new dimensions in both design and practise. Although metallic alloys and cathodic protection are well known, there is still a reluctance on the part of many end users to accept non metallic structures, largely due to lack of practical experience. In many instances there have been overwhelming technical considerations which have dictated the use of newer materials and the case history log is building rapidly. As designs and engineers become aware of the practical and economic advantages of composites of organic/inorganic nature, so applications become increasingly common realities.

I must go down to the seas again, to the lonely sea and the sky,
And all I ask is a tall ship and a star to steer her by,
And the wheel's kick and the wind's song and the white sail's
shaking,
And a grey mist on the sea's face and a grey dawn breaking.

(John Masefield)

Anticipating the Owl and the Pussycat, who favoured a beautiful pea green boat, Man first ventured seriously to sea using vegetable fibre vessels - nature's own composites. For less than two centuries the Industrial Revolution has imposed ferrous construction, with consequent acceleration in size and attendant problems of stress under kinetic loading. Subsequent advances in the technological base have made available a vast harvest of petrochemical derivatives and in achieving useful employment of these, nature's marriage of order with disorder has been harnessed in the evolution of composites - which for practical purposes can be considered as the "in" expression for Fibre Reinforced Resins.

The ancient civilisations knew the techniques for modifying vegetable, mineral and animal products to obtain useful composites. Straw and clay were combined to give building bricks, fibres and gums produced writing materials and sarcophagi. The latter perhaps indicated an important advance - environmental protection!

Vegetable fibre - papyrus, wood etc. - is durable when a living organism, but when harvested the lack of a supply of sap starts a dehydration process which eventually results in rot - a natural form of depolymerisation. The use of lacs and gums to saturate or impregnate the fibrous structure of plants was found to replace the water and prevented deterioration - coincidentally producing a primitive fibre reinforced polymeric resin composite. This principle advanced to the use of animal greases to protect timber dug-out canoes and much later the forerunners of St. Brendan made their skin-on-lath coracles more seaworthy by the application of pitch or bitumen.

With the Industrial Revolution came a near universal application of Iron as a structural material and another hazard - oxidative corrosion. The lacs, gums, pitches and bitumens were again pressed into service to give protection but, as the size of ships increased, speeds became greater and mechanical motive power became the norm, so these protective measures were found to be of only transient value. Which is not unexpected, as such protection proved essentially a surface effect, the natural fibre based structures used hitherto being absorbent thus giving a heterogeneous matrix interface with excellent adhesion.

A new technology had to be developed from the painter's art, which initially used modified oils blended with particulate solids in suspension - a logical extension from the Spar Varnishes which protected the masts of the great and graceful Tall Ships - to give greater film thickness. As manufacturing skills progressed and a realisation of the electrochemical principle of cathodic protection evolved, so these early protective paints became more sophisticated, initially with the introduction of "Zinc Dust" and other "corrosion inhibitors", culminating in the advanced polymer based Surface Coating Systems of today which are perhaps overlooked as highly developed composites in their own rights.

Many of these now incorporate fibrous elements in their formulation, ranging from base metals through glass and ceramics to polymeric fibres, giving extreme toughness and resistance to impact shock and abrasion far in excess of that attainable from the basic polymeric film base.

Small boat hulls, especially in the leisure class of boat, are now almost exclusively manufactured from Glassfibre Reinforced Polyester Resin - a trend which started during the early 1940's and which poliferated over the next 15/20 years as the ease of making small hulls from these materials became known and costs came down to level at which a great market opened up. Although many papers were written in the period 1955/1965 regarding the effect of water on resin matrices with projected calamitous failure of the resin/glass interface, no such disasters have been recorded in practise and the size of hull made in GRP continues to increase. The author recalls a number of Conferences in the decade around 1960 at which he queried the validity of research results derived from "accelerated testing" of laminates in boiling water, using polyester resins having heat distortion temperature less than 50°C, to demonstrate that GRP Hulls would not be practical - and by this time some hulls over 15 years old were still in daily use with minimal maintenance - when in practise more hydrophobic resins having higher temperature transition were already in common useage!

Today, hulls approaching 100 metres waterline length are contemplated and the military have no hesitation in operating ships constructed from these materials. Typical of these are the Royal Navy's HMS Wilton (plate 1) and HMS Brecon (plate 2). An important feature in the selection of Glass Fibre Reinforced Plastics Composites for these vessels in the non-magnetic properties, which are important in their function as minehunters.

Wilton was launched in 1972, is 50 metres long and has a displacement of 360 tonnes; Brecon was launched in 1978, has a length of 60 metres and her displacement is 625 tonnes. Comparison of maintenance and corrosion-protection for Wilton shows that her upkeep in this area is only 20% that for a comparable vessel in either wood or steel construction.

Although these ships are noteworthy for their primary construction being in single skin GRP, the manufacturing techniques were evolved over many years to give acceptably high quality to meet stringent reliability requirements. Polyvinyl chloride foam strengthening ribs form part of the structure - this having been proved to have superior qualities to other candidate materials, especially in respect of resistance to applied shear stress.

Amongst the specialist equipment carried by these vessels are electronic instrumentation, housed in GRP "towfish" to give optimum hydrodynamic performance. This is a common technique for hydrographic research and survey instrumentation - buoyancy may be incorporated where necessary using syntactic foams.

Also in the hydrographic research and survey field, buoys or floats capable of operation at depths in excess of 6,000 metres and having a volume in excess of 1m³, are commonly made from syntactic foam. These are special composites made from hallow, lightweight fillers and void-formers, uniformly dispersed in a polymeric matrix. Dependant upon operational depth and buoyancy requirements, this matrix is either a polyester or an epoxide resin. The selection of fillers and void formers is critical to achieve the desired performance. Density for a 500 metre rated system is typically 400 kilo/m³; as the depth rating increased, so does the density - a 6,000 metre rated system would be exceptional to achieve a density less than 700 kilo/m³. For depths less than 300 metres, other composites can be employed to give buoyancy relative to densities of 70 to 200 kilo/m³, using

combinations of low density plastics foams with an outer pressure shell of fibre reinforced resin - the choice of fibre being glass or carbon (graphite) with the matrix represented by polyester, epoxide or phenolic resins.

In the production of Oil from offshore sites, many examples of composites may be cited. Syntactic foam buoyancy is common use for riser pipes - the pipes which lead from the sea bed to the production platform. Service pipes within the production facility may be fabricated from GRP, Helipad deck sections, accommodation modules and miscellaneous housings all combine great specific strength with corrosion resistance and a vitally important factor in high fire risk operations - the elimination of spark hazard. The latter property may also be harnessed to advantage in glass flake filled polymer deck coverings, for which the matrix may be an elastomer such as polyurethane to give enhanced non-slip characteristics.

One potential hazard which is endemic to all organic based composites is combustibility. All organic materials will burn when subject to heat and autoignition at a critical temperature is possible in the absence of a flame source. However, a correctly fabricated thermoset or elastomer matrix will not ignite, nor contribute as a fuel source, until the temperature exceeds 350°C. This is well above the flash point of gases associated with the normal atmosphere around a rig or platform. Self extinguishing properties can be introduced into the formulation of the matrix which will reduce the incidence of propagation of a fire in the absence of an external heat source, although it is interesting to observe that such modification generally reduces the temperature by about 50°C. The poor thermal transfer of most composites make them excellent candidates where exposure to heat is unavoidable, a property which is harnessed to good effect in the construction of totally enclosed survival craft. For added security, such "lifeboats" also have a water drenching system to keep the surface cool, but in the event of failure of this drenching system and the structure actually catching fire, the temperature rise through a 6mm thick GRP canopy or hull would be less than 40°C over a 30 minute period and the flames would not penetrate the structure for a similar time period. Since wave action would itself have a flame quenching action, it is now recognised that GRP is the "natural" selection for these craft. Other specialised small boats for rescue purposes are constructed from composites, including the ubiquitous inflatables which have revolutionised diving support operations. (Plates 7 and 8)

The ever present fire hazard which prompted the evolution of the totally enclosed survival craft for the evacuation of personnel from rigs, platforms and vessels has also resulted in concern for the safety of Divers who are under saturation. Hyperbaric lifeboats are essentially decompression chambers which float at surface level; it is assumed that swell action will wash over the lifeboat to cope with surface oil fires and the general cooling action on the metallic structure will keep the temperature constant. Floatation is achieved by a vinyl foam collar covered with GRP and the same foam may also be used for thermal insulation, although this insulation may alternatively be a syntactic foam of either rigid or flexible type.

Insulation is an essential factor for diving bells and manned submersibles and the inherent low thermal conductivity, buoyancy and pressure resistance of syntactic foams have been contributory to saturation diving support. The pioneer work of Auguste Piccard some 50 years ago demonstrated the feasibility of deep diving which extended submarine operations beyond the limits of the Continental Shelves. Over the past decade, diver lock-out submersibles manufactured from GRP have been developed which have greater operating depths for a given payload compared to "conventional" steel construction. Plates 3 and 4 show the Vickers Slingsby LR4 and LR5 respectively which were developed as a result of a seven year programme carried out in association with Perry Oceanographics Inc.. The following information, given

by courtesy of Vickers Slingsby parent group, The British Underwater Engineering Ltd., is useful background to the development of GRP structures capable of withstanding external hydrostatic pressure.

	Unidirectional GRP	Bidirectional GRP	Bidirectional Twill GRP	Chopped Strand Mat GRP	HY.80 Steel
Specific Gravity	1.90	1.73	1.73	1.50	7.8
Tensile Strength	900	200	220	100	480 MN/m ²
Compressive Strength	480	160	210	100	480 MN/m ²
Shear Strength	50	70	70	-	335 MN/m ²
Inter-laminar Shear Strength	40	17	22	7	335 MN/m ²
Flexural Strength	940	240	350	110	335 MN/m ²
Tensile Modulus	36	17	13	7	210 GN/m ²
Compressive Modulus	42	19	17	7	210 GN/m ²
Shear Modulus	3.5	6.8	6.8	-	85 GN/m ²
Flexural Modulus	35	14	14	7	210 GN/m ²
Glass/Resin ratio by weight	70%	50/55%	55/60%	35%	-

The steel hulled PERRY PC-15 was used to determine design parameters for GRP hulls, the first being designated L.2. Lloyd's Register of Shipping Rules require that the pressure hull as a whole is designed such that failure should not occur until the depth of submergence exceeds 1.43 times the maximum operating depth and the hull should also be suitable for occasional dives to a proof depth of 1.11 times the normal operating depth. In the case of a pressure hull, failure is constructed to include fracture, permanent set, elastic deformation or component instability. Since PC-15 was designed to operate at 365 metres, the same operating depth was chosen for L2. The hull was therefore designed to a collapse depth of 1.43 x 1.11 x 365 metres (580 metres), or a pressure of 5.84 GN/m².

Submersibles of the PC-15 type are designed for operation close to, or on, the sea bed and as a result may be subjected to impact loading. Lloyd's Rules require that the unfactored acceleration on the submarine as a whole, due to collision, should be assumed to be not less than 3g in any direction. In addition the Rules require, if possible, for the design to be such that should local collapse of the outer fairing or structure occur, acceleration in excess of 3g for the craft as a whole should be avoided. During the associated R & D programme, tests were carried out on scale models to determine the effect on the collapse pressure of local loading, but the results were inconclusive. This is interpreted as resulting from the elastic nature of the resin matrix, since earlier experimental work by other researchers had clearly shown that collapse failure with reinforced plastics is a gradual

process, leading to buckling and seepage rather than catastrophic implosion as is observed with most metals. Fatigue testing carried out on models demonstrated a life in excess of 30,000 cycles.

On completion of the 30,000 cycles, the models were imploded and the critical pressure was found to be within the scatter band of identical models imploded on the first cycle. There was no visual degradation of the laminator, this supporting the "weeping failure" mode referred to above. A previous test programme had demonstrated that, at the maximum stress levels used in the design, creep was unlikely to be a problem; full relaxation taking place within 30 minutes of the hydrostatic pressure being removed.

Static and fatigue testing of a command module during the R and D programme showed that, although some doubt had been expressed about the stiffness of the conning tower penetration, in fact the design criteria used produced an unnecessarily stiff penetration reinforcement for L2 was reduced in area! The static test on the research and development command module showed that main acrylic viewpoint penetration was causing a bending moment in the hemihead. The reinforcement was reduced in size and it's centre of area adjusted for L2; this eliminated the bending moment. The R and D command module was subjected to 20,000 cycles at full operating depth pressure of a 3.73 MN/m² (365 metres) and 10,000 cycles at 2.42 MN/m² (237 metres). On completion of this fatigue cycle the module was pressure tested to 1.22 times the maximum design operating depth, i.e. 4.5 MN/m² (445 metres) without any sign of failure or significant visual damage.

Due to the considerably lower structural weight, a GRP pressure hull allows a higher battery payload and increased battery power compared to an equivalent steel hull; it is also non-corrosive which results in improved thermal properties of GRP provide a healthier working environment for the crew, as there is less condensation and more warmth, which, with extended underwater working periods resulting from the increased battery power, are important factors.

Calculations had shown initially that a theoretical weight saving of 1820 kilogram was possible. In practice this figure was not quite achieved and a direct comparison is not strictly possible, since the decision was taken to increase the battery power of L2 from the 46.7 KW of PC15 to 63KW. This necessitated larger battery pods, hence increasing the displacement of the submersible. The payload of an observation PC15 is approximately 450 kilogram, but she is also fitted with over 1400 kilogram of extra equipment, plus extra protection in the form of collision structure and more robust guard rails. The American Bureau of Shipping (ABS) certified PC15 and their rules do not contain the same requirements for collision! The net benefit of changing from steel to GRP is therefore about 1590 kilogram made up as follows:-

Extra Equipment	1400 Kg
Increased Payload	90 Kg
Allowance for extra protection	270 Kg
	<hr/>
	1760 Kg
Less Allowance for increased displacement of battery pods	170 Kg
Net	<hr/>
	1590 Kg

The larger submersibles, L3, L4 and L5 have confirmed the operating advantages

GRP hulls.

Having proved composites for manned operations, the development of the One Man Atmospheric Submersible (O.M.A.S.) became viable.

At a cost of around £200,000 (500,000 U.S Dollars, 2 million French Francs) O.M.A.S. (Plates 5 and 6) is not a cheap alternative to other sub-sea systems. Being an atmospheric pressure system, there is no necessity for the operator to be subjected to a lengthy period of decompression. It is claimed that, whereas a specialist diver requires at least 6 months intensive instruction, it is possible for an OMAS operator to be trained in 20 hours. Operational capability of 600 metres means that all sectors of the continental shelves can be serviced by these devices.

Practical offshore oil production to date has been limited to water depths below 200 metres, this being the extent to which fixed platforms have been technically viable. The development of buoyant structures has resulted in a requirement for special moorings, which has been met by special cables comprising of polyester and aramid fibres contained within a protective sheath of polyolefin or polyurethane. Conventional cable construction requires strands of fibres to be twisted to give sufficient elasticity to withstand snatch loads but the "linear composite" concept allows the use of parallel fibres protected by a wear resistant sheath, giving a much higher breaking load for a given diameter than conventional construction.

<u>Cable Type</u>	<u>Diameter</u>	<u>Wt in air Kg/m</u>	<u>Breaking Load</u>	<u>Breaking Load</u>	<u>Wt in air Kg/m</u>	<u>Diameter</u>
Linear Composite Aramid Core	90mm	6.0	600 T	500 T	5	83mm
Linear Composite Polyester Core	90mm	5.6	200 T	500 T	14.4	140mm
Braided Nylon	90mm	5.5	170 T	500 T	19.5	170mm
3 Strand Nylon	90mm	5.0	135 T	100 T	3.2	70mm
3 Strand Polyester	90mm	6.2	110 T	500 T	-	-
3 Strand Polypropylene	90mm	3.6	90 T	100 T	3.8	76mm
3 Strand Manilla	90mm	5.5	60 T	500 T	6.0	88mm
Steel Strand Cables	90mm	26.0	500 T	100 T	-	-
				500 T	4.15	96mm
				100 T	10	120mm
				500 T	26	90mm
				100 T	4.9	40mm

The exception properties of the Aramid core linear composites can be readily appreciated, but the Polyester core homologues have widespread application. The smooth surface of the sheathing discourages marine growth in mooring applications, reducing drag coefficients significantly especially in very deep water. Scientific data collection buoys in greater than 500 metres depth can be reduced in physical size by the utilisation of these more compact and lightweight moorings, which in turn reduces snatch forces and windage with

consequent security to the moorings themselves. The buoy structures themselves can be GRP, making for ease of deployment and reduction in maintenance.

Sheathed linear composites also have important applications above deck. Icing of rigging is believed to be a contributory factor in the loss of small vessels due to build up of top weight causing instability and consequent capsizing. Quite apart from a prime weight saving by a factor of 3:2 for rigging of equivalent strength compared to steel, sheathed composites shed ice very easily when vibrated and should lead to yet another contribution to Safety at Sea.

The author wishes to record his thanks to many friends both in the plastics industry, oil exploration and production companies and marine interests in providing information and opinions which have assisted in the compilation of this paper. These are too numerous to name individually, but the provision of illustrations and slides is acknowledged from Slingsby Engineering Ltd., B.P. Chemicals Ltd., ICI Linear Composites Ltd., Aberglen Holdings Ltd. as well as Bathos Developments Ltd. and Lite Sea Marketing Ltd.

Plate 1 : HMS Wilton

Plate 2 : HMS Brecon

Plate 3 : Vickers Slingsby LR4 Submersible

Plate 4 : Vickers Slingsby L R 5 Submersible

Plate 5 : Schematic Diagram of Vickers-Slingsby O.M.A.S.

Plate 6 : Vickers-Sungby O.M.A.S.

Plate 7 : ABERGLEN 8 metre Totally Enclosed
Survival Craft emerges from a
Kerosene fire after 10 minutes exposure.

Plate 8 : ABERGLEN GORDON 6 metre fast rescue craft.
Rigid centrehull with inflatable sidewalls.